

AFRICAN TRADITIONAL VALUE AND GLOBALIZATION AS PREDICTORS OF FUNCTIONAL FAMILY BACKGROUND AMONG PUBLIC UNIVERSITY UNDERGRADUATES IN OGUN STATE

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Abstract

This study examined the examined Africa traditional value and globalization as predictors of functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State. The population of the study comprised all undergraduates of Tai Solarin Federal University of Education with a sample of 400 undergraduate students using a stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using the Africa Traditional Value Questionnaire (ATVQ), Globalization Questionnaire (GQ), and Functional Family Background Questionnaire (FFBQ) with reliability coefficients of .78, .77, and .78 respectively. Findings from the study revealed no significant relationship between African traditional value and functional family background ($r = -0.001, p > 0.05$), a significant relationship between globalization and functional family background ($r = .135, p < 0.05$), and a significant combined influence of African traditional value and globalization on functional family background ($F = 3.519, p < 0.05$). The study concluded that functional family background among undergraduates is shaped by both traditional and modern influences, but other unexamined factors may also play substantial roles. It was recommended, among others, that policymakers, educational planners, and university management should develop programmes that integrate positive African cultural values with beneficial global practices.

Keywords:

African value, globalization, family, higher education.

Introduction

The family is universally acknowledged as the most fundamental social institution responsible for shaping the attitudes, personality, values, and behavioural outcomes of individuals in society. It represents the first point of socialisation, nurturing, protection, emotional support, and character formation for children and young adults. According to Mignonette and Robert (2019), the family operates as an interconnected system in which the behaviour, decisions, and emotional expressions of one member influence the overall functioning of the entire family unit. Chineyemba (2023) similarly described the family as the basic unit of society and the locus for procreation, reproduction, socialisation, and the education of children. A well-functioning family environment therefore promotes emotional wellbeing, social competence, moral stability, and academic progress, all of which are particularly critical during the transitional stage of higher education.

Traditional African family value emphasize interconnectedness, collective responsibility, respect for elders, moral discipline, and communal living, all of which contribute to the stability and functionality of family systems. The African family is not merely a biological unit but a moral and social institution that nurtures core virtues such as respect for elders, honesty, hospitality, and community service. Imoh and Omidiji (2026) affirmed this view, noting that Nigeria's traditional education system rooted entirely in the family and community sought to produce individuals who are honest, respectable, cooperative, and conformed to the social order, with its cardinal goals explicitly encompassing character building, respect for authority, and active community participation as foundational outcomes of child development. Globalization is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that describes the increasing interconnectedness and interdependence of societies across the world. It encompasses economic, political, technological, and cultural dimensions, linking local and global experiences in unprecedented ways. Giddens (1990) as cited in Alkharafi and Alsabah (2025), noted that globalization is a social process through which local events are shaped by global forces, and vice versa, resulting in profound changes in lifestyles, social norms, and cultural practices.

Adegboyega et al., (2026) examined the impact of globalisation on family relationships and dynamics as expressed by married adults in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study highlighted that globalisation does not merely influence family structures but actively reshapes relational processes within families, producing adaptive rather than purely disruptive transformations. Married adults were found to adopt coping strategies such as improved communication, role renegotiation, reliance on social support systems, and preservation of cultural values in navigating the demands of a globalised society. Chineyemba (2023) found that changing value systems in Nigeria impact family time and relationships, as ICT and media expose children to values alien to African cultural ethos, posing serious challenges to effective parenting. Traditional Nigerian values such as chastity, family name and reputation, unity, and mutual respect are gradually eroding under the pressures of modernity, contributing to moral decay and rising insecurity.

The family remains the primary institution responsible for transmitting values, social norms, emotional support, and moral guidance to young people. Traditionally, African families were characterized by strong kinship ties, communal living, shared responsibilities, and respect for elders, which promoted family cohesion and social stability. However, the increasing influence of globalization through social media, digital technology, migration, and exposure to foreign cultures has introduced new lifestyles and value systems that are gradually reshaping family relationships and cultural orientations. This situation is particularly evident among public university undergraduates in Ogun State, who are increasingly exposed to both African traditional values and global influences, creating concerns about the functionality of their family backgrounds in contemporary society.

If this trend continues without adequate understanding and intervention, it may contribute to weakened family bonds, poor communication, reduced moral guidance, identity conflicts, and diminished emotional support among young people, with possible implications for their personal, social, and academic development. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate African traditional values and globalization as predictors of functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine Africa traditional value and globalization as predictors of functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State. Specifically, the sought to examine:

1. the relationship between African traditional value and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State
2. the relationship between globalisation and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State
3. the combined influence of African traditional value and globalisation on functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

- H0₁** There is no significant relationship between African traditional value and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State.
- H0₂** There is no significant relationship between globalisation and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State.
- H0₃** There is no significant combined influence of African traditional value and globalisation on functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive research design of survey type. The population of this study comprised all undergraduates of Tai Solarin Federal University of Education (TASFUED). A sample of 400 undergraduate student across five department in the College of Specialised and Professional Education were selected using stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using the Africa Traditional Value Questionnaire (ATVQ), Globalization Questionnaire (GQ), and Functional Family Background Questionnaire (FFBQ) with reliability coefficients of .78, .77, and .78 respectively which shows the instruments are reliable. Data collected for this study were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), and Multiple Regression all at .05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between African traditional value and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State.

Table 1

Pearson's Correlation Showing Relationship Between African Traditional Value and Functional Family Background

Variables	N	\bar{X}	Std.	r	Sig (p)	Remark
African Traditional Value	380	3.31	0.582	-	.978	Not Significant
Functional Family Background		3.40	0.523	0.001		

The result in table 1 revealed that there was no significant relationship between African traditional value and functional family background ($r = -0.001$, $p = .978$). The negative correlation coefficient indicates a negligible inverse relationship, suggesting that an increase in African traditional value may be associated with a slight decrease in functional family background. Therefore, the relationship was not statistically significant because the p-value ($p = .978$) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between African Traditional Value and Functional Family Background was sustained.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between globalization and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State

Table 2

Pearson's Correlation Showing the Relationship Between Globalization and Functional Family Background

Variables	N	\bar{X}	Std.	r	Sig (p)	Remark
Globalization	380	3.40	0.577	0.135	.009	Significant
Functional Family Background		3.40	0.523			

The result in table 2 revealed that there was a significant relationship between globalization and functional family background ($r = .135, p = .009$). The positive correlation coefficient indicates a weak positive relationship, suggesting that an increase in globalization may be associated with an increase in functional family background. Therefore, the relationship was statistically significant because the p-value ($p = .009$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between globalization and Functional Family Background was rejected.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant combined influence of African traditional value and globalization on functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State.

Table 3

Regression Analysis Showing the Combined Influence of African Traditional Value and Globalization on Functional Family Background

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p	Remark
Regression	1.903	2	0.951	3.519	.031	Significant
Residual	101.935	377	0.270			
Total	103.838	379				

$R = .135^a, R^2 = .018, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .013, \text{RMSE} = .520$

a. Predictors: (Constant), African Traditional Value and Globalization

b. Dependent Variable: Functional Family Background

The result in Table 3 revealed that there was a significant combined influence of African traditional value and globalization on functional family background ($F = 3.519, p = .031$). The regression coefficient ($R = .135$) indicates a weak positive combined relationship between African traditional value, globalisation, and functional family background. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .018$) implies that African traditional value and globalization jointly accounted for 1.8% of the variance in functional family background, while the remaining 98.2% may be attributed to other variables not included in the model. Therefore, the combined influence was statistically significant because the p-value ($p = .031$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant combined influence of African Traditional Value and Globalization on Functional Family Background was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of hypothesis one revealed that there was no significant relationship between African traditional value and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State. This implies that family functionality among undergraduates may depend more on economic, parental, psychological, and environmental factors than on traditional values alone. This finding agrees with Chineyemba (2023) who found that cultural assimilation through modernization has drastically altered family values in Nigeria, resulting in reduced quality time between parents and children, largely due to economic demands.

The finding of hypothesis two revealed that there was a significant relationship between globalization and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State. This implies that exposure to globalisation through technological advancement, education, media exposure, intercultural communication, and improved access to information may positively shape family functionality. The finding agrees with Adegboyega (2026) who found that global economic pressures and lifestyle changes significantly influence family cohesion and marital satisfaction in contemporary Nigerian society.

The finding of hypothesis three revealed that there was a significant combined influence of African traditional value and globalization on functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State. This implies that although the combined influence was statistically significant, the explanatory power of the variables was relatively small, suggesting that several other factors not captured in the study may explain functional family background among undergraduates. Chineyemba (2023) found that families operate simultaneously within the pull of traditional communal responsibilities and the pressures of modern economic realities, with neither force operating independently.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that African traditional value did not significantly relate with functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State, indicating that adherence to traditional values alone may not necessarily determine family functionality among students in contemporary society. The finding suggests that family functioning among undergraduates may be influenced more by other social, economic, parental, and environmental factors beyond traditional cultural values. The study further concluded that globalization had a significant positive relationship with functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State. This implies that increased exposure to globalization, such as access to information, technological advancement, education, and intercultural experiences, may contribute positively to family functionality. Finally, the study concluded that African traditional value and globalisation jointly exerted a significant influence on functional family background, although their combined contribution was relatively small. This suggests that functional family background among undergraduates is shaped by both traditional and modern influences, but other unexamined factors may also play substantial roles. Therefore, family functionality among undergraduates should be viewed as a multidimensional phenomenon shaped by interacting cultural, social, and global dynamics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Universities, parents, and community leaders should focus on promoting practical family support systems rather than relying solely on traditional values. This can be achieved through regular family counselling programmes, parenting

- education, and student support initiatives that strengthen communication, emotional support, and healthy family relationships.
2. Educational institutions and families should encourage the positive use of globalisation tools and opportunities. This can be achieved by promoting digital literacy, access to educational technologies, constructive social media engagement, and exposure to global knowledge that enhances family communication and support systems.
 3. Policymakers, educational planners, and university management should develop programmes that integrate positive African cultural values with beneficial global practices. This can be achieved through value-based educational programmes, family life education, cultural sensitisation workshops, and curriculum initiatives that balance indigenous values with modern realities.

Contributions to Knowledge

This study contributed to knowledge in the following ways:

1. The study provided empirical evidence on the relationship between African traditional value, globalization, and functional family background among public university undergraduates in Ogun State, thereby enriching existing literature in educational planning and family studies.
2. The study expanded understanding of how traditional cultural values and global influences interact in shaping family functionality among young adults in contemporary society.
3. The study contributed methodologically by combining correlation and regression analysis to examine both individual and combined influences of African traditional value and globalization on functional family background.

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